

FRACTURE AND FAILURE PROCESSES IN PULTRUDED UNIDIRECTIONAL GRP USED AS CABLE STRENGTH MEMBERS

R.Leetham, S.N.Kukureka

The University of Birmingham, School of Metallurgy and Materials, Edgbaston, Birmingham, B15 2TT, UK

ABSTRACT

In order to establish the reliability of dielectric cables there is a need to understand the failure processes occurring in pultruded GRP used as a strength member material. The use of GRP as a cable strength member is not a common application for this material because the strength member maintains a constant tensile load for the duration of life. The different methods of observing damage development in composite materials, both qualitative and quantitative are discussed in relation to studying the effects of fatigue testing of small diameter pultruded GRP rod.

Keywords: Dielectric cables, pultruded rod, GRP, damage development.

1. INTRODUCTION

The great increase in the need for faster, more efficient telecommunications has encouraged the use of optical fibre communication systems. Optical fibres exhibit several advantages over the original copper signal carrying systems[1] including a greater information-carrying capacity. A conventional telecommunication cable that has an information-carrying capacity similar to an optical fibre cable is much larger than the optical cable. Along with the increasing use of optical fibres there is also a growing interest in dielectric cables: cables that contain no conducting components. An optical fibre system lends itself well to this application because of the immunity to electromagnetic noise that glass fibres display[2]. The development of a dielectric cable does not end with the means of obtaining a non-conducting signal carrier medium. Cables contain a great many other components designed to allow the optical fibre to perform as effectively as possible for the duration of its life, all of which need to be not only non-conducting but also able to provide the properties necessary to protect the fibres.

1.1 Dielectric cables

The use of dielectric cable is desirable in high voltage areas, including the following examples: (a) installation along railway lines; (b) installation in pipelines; (c) aerial cables; (d) use in countries where electrical storms are commonplace. Often the distribution of these cables make use of existing networks, electricity pylons for example, reducing the installation costs as much as possible. The main function of cabling is to provide the optical fibres with adequate protection from damage during installation and when in service. Even small levels of damage can greatly impair the performance of the optical fibre by causing an increase in the attenuation of the electromagnetic signal[2]. Glass is a brittle material and exhibits near perfect elasticity up to the breaking point. The bulk material strength of flawless glass is quite high but this can be drastically reduced by the introduction of a flaw. A bare fibre can have very high strength immediately after drawing but this tends to deteriorate very quickly,

under normal atmospheric conditions by as much as two orders of magnitude[3]. Flaws tend to be produced during the manufacture of the fibre by mechanical means but they can also be produced, and undergo slow growth, by the combined action of water and stress. This is known as stress corrosion. Most cables will include some form of water-protective barrier to avoid the possibility of fibre failure occurring by the process of stress corrosion.

The optical fibre cables are often installed in ducts that run underground. A high tensile strength is required, especially for long cables, where the tension needed to pull the cable through the duct increases as the process continues. The tension required is a function of the coefficient of friction between the cable sheath and the connecting surfaces of the duct. In long straight ducts the tension increases linearly with length but if the duct has a number of curves then there is the addition of an exponential increase to the pulling tension[3]. It has been shown that to enable the optical fibres to maintain long-term reliability, the cable should not be strained to elongations outside the 0.3-0.8% range[4]. Thus, it is clear that a load-bearing component is essential to the provision of adequate mechanical properties for the optical cable. The cable strength member provides the cable with sufficient tensile strength to survive installation and is preferably made from a material which exhibits elasticity up to at least 1% elongation. There are other features of the strength member that are also seen as desirable for use in an optical fibre cable such as a high Young's modulus, although the cable does require some flexibility to ease installation; materials with a high Young's modulus are inherently stiff. This problem can be overcome by using stranded or bunched material of smaller cross-sections which results in a more flexible cable than if only solid material has been used.

Figure 1. A Schematic diagram of a dielectric cable with a GRP strength member designed for installation along railway lines.[Courtesy of BNR Europe Ltd.]

1.2 GRP strength members

The material most commonly used for the cable strength member is steel, in solid or braided forms. An alternative material, that can supply sufficient mechanical properties, is required for dielectric cables. These strength members may be based on glass reinforced thermosets - epoxies and polyesters - or on aramid fibres such as Kevlar although other materials such as carbon fibre and plastics monofilaments are also used[2][3][4]. In this case the study is limited to the use of glass fibre reinforced plastics (GRP) with diameters in the range of 1.5 mm to 5 mm. Figure 1 shows an example of a dielectric cable with a GRP strength member, that has been designed to be installed along the railway lines. In order to provide the necessary mechanical properties a high volume fraction of fibres is needed, in the region of 60-70%. The high strengths that are needed in cable applications are obtained from the GRP by using unidirectional, continuous glass reinforcements that run the length of the cable. The GRP rod that is used to form the strength member is manufactured by the pultrusion process. A schematic diagram of the pultrusion process can be seen in Figure 2. A continuous strand roving of glass is unwound from a reel and then passed through a resin bath. The excess resin is removed and the impregnated glass then passes through a heated barrel which ends in

a shaped die. Here the resin is cured and final shaping of the pultruded rod is achieved. The end result is a continuous, highly aligned GRP rod with a large volume fraction of glass which exhibits high strength combined with low weight. By this method long lengths of up to 25 km of continuous GRP rod can be produced which are ideal for use in cables.

Figure 2. A schematic diagram of the pultrusion process.

The use of GRP as a cable strength member is not, as yet, a common application for this material. The major stress acting on the cable is a tensile stress. The application of a constant unvarying load for extended periods of time is an unusual requirement for GRP which is usually used in a laminated form. Cables generally have a specified lifetime of 25 years although lifetimes can be as high as 40 years[4]. In order to guarantee that the cable will survive for this length of time the reliability of GRP as a cable strength member requires investigation. This has been further emphasised by the discovery of a premature failure in GRP radio antennae guy ropes[5][6]. This application for GRP can be compared with that of a cable strength member in that the GRP is sustaining a tensile load for long periods of time. Failures were observed in the guy ropes after only a few years at loads that were fraction of the predicted breaking load. The fracture surfaces were found to be uncharacteristically smooth and planar. GRP failures tend to have a fibrous or brush-like appearance. The smooth surface was thought to be the product of the application of a tensile stress in the presence of an aggressive environment: a stress corrosion failure. This observation indicated that there was the possibility of the GRP strength member failing by a stress corrosion mechanism.

An understanding of the mechanical reliability of cable strength members requires a knowledge of the possible fracture processes and failure mechanisms. As mentioned, there is the possibility of failure due to a stress corrosion mechanism. There is also the possibility of a fatigue failure. Aerial cables, in certain conditions, undergo what are known as 'aeolian vibrations'. These vibrations are induced by the wind and have been observed in overhead shield wires[7][8]. Overhead shield wires are used in connection with transmission cables, their major function being to protect the current carrying conductors from the dangers of lightning strikes. The aeolian vibrations induced in the shield wires can be transmitted to the ground through the support structures and can result in the loosening of bolts in the structure. Abrasion of the shield wire under the clamps is another effect of the vibrations caused by the relative movement of the wire. Severe vibration can result in fatigue of the wire at the support points. This example indicates that the cyclic, dynamic movement of the wind induced vibration in an aerial optical cable may have detrimental effects on the GRP strength member.

Possible failures by stress corrosion and/or fatigue, as a result of wind induced vibrations, indicate that there is a need to establish the reliability of the GRP strength member. This may be best achieved by considering the failure mechanisms that occur in the GRP strength members with the aim of

understanding the damage development. This paper will deal with the available methods of measuring damage development specifically in the area of fatigue testing of GRP. From a knowledge of the damage accumulation in GRP fatigue specimens then it is hoped that life predictions can be made.

2. DAMAGE DEVELOPMENT

2.1 Damage development in GRP

Unlike metals, fibre reinforced composites do not tend to fail in a linear elastic manner with the formation of a single dominant crack when fatigued. A range of damage is produced including the following: fibre failures; resin cracking; interfacial debonding; delamination between laminate plies[6][9-13]. All of these forms of damage are interconnected making the identification of crack paths difficult. Nor is the damage limited to the localised region of the crack tip, although damage does tend to be more severe in this area, but is widespread throughout the specimen. Reinforced plastics are inhomogeneous and in some cases highly anisotropic. The high degree of anisotropy tends to influence the stress distributions at the crack tip which results in crack propagation in composite materials tending to follow complex paths[13][14]. Damage in GRP can develop as early as the first fatigue cycle[6][13] which is far removed from observations of metallic materials where a large proportion of the fatigue life of the material is taken up in the initiation of a fatigue crack. The presence of microstructural defects in GRP results in a high degree of damage initiation. Defects such as resin rich areas, misaligned fibres and voids in the matrix material all act as sites for damage initiation. The presence of an interface in a composite material has a significant effect on the initiation and propagation of cracks. Debonding and other stress concentrations at the interface act as strong initiation sites and this results in the rapid initiation and growth of cracks[10]. The interface can also have a beneficial effect on the propagation of cracks acting as a barrier, blunting or redirecting the approaching crack. Cracks that have formed in the matrix are arrested by a hard, strong reinforcing phase: the greater the difference in strength the greater the crack arrest[14]. For this reason the strength gradient at the interface may be seen as more important than the interfacial bond strength.

2.2 A damage variable

As mentioned in section 2.1, identification of crack paths can be difficult due to the range of damage interconnecting. Observation of the damage development is needed to enable an understanding of the processes involved in fatigue damage development. Non-destructive test methods such as optical microscopy, ultrasonic C-scanning, X-ray inspection and infra-red thermography, play a large part in the determination of fatigue damage development.

The damage development can be simply observed through a travelling microscope[15] or by the production of replica of certain stages of the fatigue test. The microscopic damage can be reproduced on cellulose acetate replica tape combined with the use of acetone. The replicas that are produced can be examined under an optical microscope or under a scanning electron microscope(SEM). By making replicas after different fractions of life a picture of the damage development can be constructed. Jessen and Plumtree[12] used this technique to observe the fatigue damage produced at various stress levels and were able to determine the sequence and predominant failure mechanisms that were operating. Another optical method by which the fatigue damage can be observed is by the use of a high intensity light source[16]. This is shone through the composite and the damage can then be photographed. This technique can be improved by using a coloured dye penetrant to provide a colour enhanced contrast of the damage.

The attenuation of an ultrasonic beam that has passed through the specimen and then related to the damage present in the composite is another method of observing damage development[11]. A requirement of the technique is the need for a transfer medium, usually water, through which the ultrasonic beam can be transmitted. This particular technique is useful for detecting delamination and edge cracking in laminated composites, but not in pultruded GRP of small diameters. X-rays inspection[11] relies on the use of an x-ray opaque penetrant, such as zinc iodide[16], being introduced to the composite which allows high contrast photographs to be produced of the damage. As this method is useful for detecting in-plane damage such as transverse cracks, if used in association with the ultrasonic technique a fairly comprehensive picture of the damage development

can be constructed.

Plastics materials are susceptible to hysteresis heating when cycled [17]. The heat generated from the hysteresis heating and also the frictional heating caused by the differential movement of cracks can be detected by infra-red thermography [11]. Resolutions comparable to those obtained from ultrasonics can be achieved but they are rather less than those achieved by the use of x-rays. The main advantage of the system is that the specimen can remain fixed in the test machine, removing the need to interrupt the test.

All of the methods mentioned above generally involve a qualitative view of the damage development. The characterisation of composite damage accumulation so that questions relating to the strength and life of composite materials can be answered, requires the development of an analytical technique. This involves the development of a damage variable which can take account of the accumulation of damage as a fatigue test continues. A direct measure of damage accumulation is a long and difficult process but an indirect method of assessment such as the measurement of a physical quantity of the material is a more practical approach to the problem of obtaining a damage variable. The influence of the damage on a physical quantity of the material can be measured and then used to define the damage variable [18][12]. Work by Naeem [15] has shown that there is an analytical relationship between the propagation of damage in glass reinforced laminates and the change in compliance that occurs when fatigued. Thus, it would appear that the measure of stiffness of a composite material may be a good choice for the physical quantity required for the development of a damage variable [19][18][15][12]. As the damage increases the stiffness monotonically decreases and it is a physical quantity that can be easily measured without further degrading the test specimen. Thus the damage variable, D can be defined as follows [12][18]:

$$D = 1 - \frac{E}{E_0} \quad (1)$$

where E_0 is the elastic modulus of the material in the undamaged state and E is the apparent elasticity in the damaged state. It follows that for a material in an undamaged state the damage variable, $D = 0$ and that at a critical state of damage at which catastrophic failure occurs, $D = D_c$. Jessen and Plumtree [12] used this definition to obtain a damage level ($D = 0.2$) at which they could define failure. This enabled them to reduce the testing time necessary to obtain a result of failure without having to resort to causing the complete, catastrophic failure of the specimen.

2.3 Life prediction

Ye [18] introduced the damage variable to define the degree of phenomenological damage in a composite material in order to develop a fatigue damage accumulation model. The objective of developing the model is to enable the prediction of the residual properties of a composite that has undergone a known loading and environmental history. Since the stiffness is known to be linearly related to the level of damage within a composite material then the observation of the change in stiffness of a composite material during fatigue will give an indication of the accumulation of damage.

Using results obtained from Refs. 19 and 20, Ye [18] constructed normalised stiffness reduction curves for composite materials that had undergone tensile fatigue loading. The curve indicated three regions where the stiffness reduction occurred at different rates. Initially there was a rapid decrease in the stiffness of the material which was followed by an intermediate region where the rate of stiffness reduction was much lower. The final region showed a sudden increase in the reduction rate which was quickly followed by failure of the specimen. Applying the definition for the damage variable (Equation 1) a curve showing the damage development in the composite specimen can be constructed. As expected, considering the linear relationship between the damage variable and the stiffness of the material, the damage development curve also shows three regions: rapid damage development followed by a decrease in the rate and concluding with a sudden increase in the rate of damage development. Ye suggested that for most composites this curve could be effectively split into two regions, N_1 and N_2 . The first region, N_1 , shows damage development initially occurring at a rapid rate but also shows the rate gradually decreasing. The beginning of the second region can be identified by the abrupt change in the damage curve that is considered to be at a critical level of damage. From this point the damage development occurs at a rapidly increasing rate. In some composites the duration of the second part of the curve tends to be very short, the duration of the first

part of the curve taking up the majority of the specimen lifetime. This observation forms the basis for the suggested means of predicting the life of a specimen. Ye proposed that the following equation for calculating the duration of the initial part of the damage curve, N_1 may be used to predict the lifetime of a composite material if the critical damage level can be determined by a proper criterion:

$$N_1 = \frac{D_c^{n+1}}{(n+1) C \sigma_{\max}^{2n}} \quad (2)$$

where D_c is the critical damage level, σ_{\max} is the maximum stress and n and C are material constants.

The above equation can be used to aid prediction of the lifetime of pultruded GRP strength members and hence establish the reliability of optical cables. With dielectric cables often having specified lifetimes of 25 years or more, the need to ascertain the GRP failure processes can clearly be seen. This will involve the investigation of the damage development observed in small diameter pultruded GRP. The best method of achieving this appears to be the quantitative approach of the determination of a damage variable. The indirect method of measuring the reduction in stiffness caused as a result of fatigue loading is a technique to which the pultruded GRP is well suited. The other qualitative methods of damage characterisation are more applicable to use on laminated GRP than on the small diameter pultruded GRP but are still useful as a means of observing the types of damage produced in a fatigue specimen.

Acknowledgements

The author would like to thank BNR Europe Ltd. for both their support and their expertise in the area of cable design. Thanks also go to John Shaw Ltd., Northern Telecom, Canada and BNR Europe Ltd. for the supply of pultruded rod and to the Science and Engineering Research Council for their support.

References

1. Sandbank, C.P., *Optical Fibre Communication Systems*, John Wiley and Sons, Chichester, England, 1980, pp 1.
2. Senior, J., *Optical Fibre Communications*, Prentice/Hall International, 1985, pp133.
3. Foord, S.G., *Optical Fibre Communication Systems*, John Wiley and Sons, Chichester, England, 1980, pp 70.
4. Bark, P.R., Lawrence, D.O., *Optical Fibre Transmission*, Howard W Sams and Co., USA, 1986, pp93.
5. Scanlan, I.F., *Long Term Fatigue Failure of Fibrespan Cable*, Unpublished report No. 412/048/88, STL plc., Harlow, 1988.
6. Mandell, J.F., *Fatigue Behaviour of Fibre-Resin Composites*, in *Developments in Reinforced Plastics 2*, Applied Science, 1982, pp67.
7. Whapham, R., Champa, R.J., *Wind Induced Vibrations of Overhead Shield Wires*, Presented at PCEA Engineering and Operating Conference, Los Angeles, USA, March, 1983.
8. Grimado, P.B., *Dynamic Characteristics of Aerial Fiber Optic Cable*, *Optical Engineering*, Vol. 30, No. 6, pp 808-814 1991.
9. Hahn, H.T., *Fatigue Behaviour and Life Prediction of Composite Laminates*, *Composite Materials: Testing and Design (5th Conference) ASTM STP 674*, S.W. Tsai (ed.), American Society

for Testing and Materials pp 383-417, 1979.

10. Dew-Hughes, D., Way, J.L., *Fatigue of Fibre-Reinforced Plastics: a Review*, Composites, Vol. 4, No. 7, pp 167-173, 1973.

11. Curtis, P.T., *The Fatigue Behaviour of Fibrous Composite Materials*, Journal of Strain Analysis, Vol. 24, No. 4, pp 235-244, 1989.

12. Jessen, S.M., Plumtree, A., *Fatigue Damage Accumulation in Pultruded Glass/Polyester Rods*, Composites, Vol. 20, No. 6, pp 559-567, 1989.

13. Harris, B., *Fatigue and Accumulation of Damage in Reinforced Plastics*, Composites, Vol. 8, No. 4, pp 214-220, 1977.

14. Reifsnider, K., *Fatigue Behaviour of Composite Materials*, International Journal of Fracture, Vol. 16, No.6, pp 563-583, 1980.

15. Naeem, M., *Fatigue Damage-Compliance Relationship for GRP Composites*, Composites, Vol. 20, No. 6, pp 589-592, 1989.

16. O'Brien, T.K., Rigamonti, M., Zanotti, C., *Tension Fatigue Analysis and Life Prediction for Composite Laminates*, International Journal of Fatigue, Vol. 11, No. 6, pp 379-393, 1989.

17. Hertzberg, R.W., Manson, J.A., *Fatigue of Engineering Plastics*, Academic Press, New York, 1980.

18. Lin Ye, *On Fatigue Damage Accumulation and Material Degradation in Composite Materials*, Composite Science and Technology, Vol. 36, No. 4, pp 339-350, 1989.

19. Wang, S.S., Chim, E.S-M., *Fatigue Damage and Degradation in Random Short Fibre SMC Composite*, Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 17, No. 3, pp 114-134, 1983.

20. Highsmith, A.L., Stinchcomb, W.W., Reifsnider, K.L., *In Effects of Defects in Composite Materials*, ASTM STP-836, pp 194, 1984.